

FEATURES OF A SIMPLE STILL LIFE WORK COMPOSED OF TWO OR MORE GEOMETRIC OBJECTS ON A NEUTRAL BACKGROUND

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Soliev Khakimjon Zokirjonovich

senior teacher at the Department of Fine Arts and Engineering Graphics of NamSU

ELSEVIER

Abstract: This article talks about the goals and tasks of painting in higher educational institutions prepared by a fine art teacher, the special importance of pencil drawing in realistic painting, the artist's palette, the technology of working with grisaille in watercolor paint. Also, the stages of painting and the tasks performed in them are described

Keywords:.. Science of painting, purpose, tasks, still life, pencil drawing, observation, description, object plane, watercolor paint, painter's palette, brush, grisaille, painting stages

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Introduction

60111200 - Fine arts and engineering graphics prepared by a visual arts teacher for secondary general education schools, due to the fact that the study period is currently three years in the bachelor's education fields, painting training will be two years. At first, he studied painting for four or five years. That's why it helps students to become familiar with the goals and tasks of painting science from the beginning of their studies. Development of specific instructions and recommendations for each subject, rational use of foreign educational technologies, accelerated advanced methods of teaching are required.

The goal of teaching painting is to convey to students and young people that painting has its own leading character as the basis of all fine arts, to arm the future art teacher with the theory and practical skills of painting, to develop creative abilities, to form knowledge, skills and abilities suitable for fine art, and consists of thorough preparation for pedagogical activity²⁰¹.

Literature review

The task of science is to educate future teachers of fine arts in an artistic way, to improve their artistic taste, to familiarize them with works of fine art, to raise their thoughts and judgments about sophistication, to create the skills to see, read and understand works of fine art. Also, it is to form the skills of students, future artists - pedagogues, to observe and analyze, correctly describe, perceive the

²⁰¹ Painting science program. BD – 5110800 - 3.02.2020. 2- p.

environment, existence, perceive color, and create painting works. The art of realistic painting aims to develop the ability to express existence in true images.

Painting is one of the main types of fine art, which is created by applying paint to a specific surface. Painting is mainly divided into two types: easel painting and majestic painting. This tutorial mainly covers the issue of easel painting, the technology of short-term and long-term painting with watercolor, gouache and oil paints, the ability to read works of art, the formation of colors in nature, the effect on the human body, light and shade, the laws of perspective, the texture of objects and others will be described in detail. Because, the future teacher of fine arts should have sufficient knowledge, drawing skills, skills and qualifications about painting with easel. Educating the young generation through works of art is the main task of a visual arts teacher.

It is known that a person is surrounded by colors from the day he was born. Tevarak - the existence that surrounds us is covered in different colors. Every thing or thing that makes up existence has its own color. Decorative decorations on the streets, buildings, cars, electronic panels and transformers, green trees, various trees, flowers and all such things are among them. There is no area in our daily life that is not affected by color. Because as long as the sun shines in the sky, the whole world is made of different colors. The duty of a painting is to surprise the viewer and give him aesthetic pleasure by depicting the existence, all things in it, creatures - beings, reflecting it as it is. At this point, the following words of Pascal can be considered as an assessment of the painting. "What a strange and surprising thing is a painting - a still life: the viewer who did not enjoy the original copy will be excited by how much he will enjoy it."²⁰²

Pencil drawing is considered the basis of all types of fine art. In particular, the basis of painting is pencil drawing, and the long-term practical training of the painting lesson begins with finding the line drawing of objects correctly. The pencil drawing introduces the shape, size, structural structure, material and important features of the object that determine its character.

If we compare pencil drawing, which is the basis of all types of fine arts, with such disciplines as drawing and drawing geometry, its characteristics become more evident. First, the artist can visualize the image with his eyes and depict it with his hand in a short time. Secondly, the artist shows the external main features of the object in the image, its materiality, size, light, spatial location, etc. Thirdly, the pencil drawing not only depicts the various external signs of the object, but also expresses the internal content of the object and evokes certain thoughts and feelings in the observer.

²⁰² O'. Abdullaev. Still life in painting. - T.: 2014. p. 3.

"Pencil drawing is an image made by hand on the basis of outlines, lines and spots, which are graphic means of representation.", begins by observing objects, creatures and beings²⁰³.

Follow-up implies systematic and goal-oriented learning. The meaningful image of a thing is formed in our mind based on imagination. On the basis of this figure, the external signs of things and objects are expressed. One of the characteristics of observation is learning, knowing and understanding. Observation directly depends on people's ability to see. When starting to work on the image, the student carefully studies and analyzes the composition. Determines the specific structure and characteristic features of the composition.

It is called analysis when the student expresses his idea in a descriptive way, i.e., the structure of the depicted objects, the interrelationship of their parts, and their spatial position. The process of describing things consists of observation, detailed analysis and description. Students need to learn to observe things in order to accurately and convincingly describe their appearance. Just as an elementary school student learns to read and write, a student with regular practice can learn the rules of painting.

First of all, each student needs to be familiar with watercolor paint, its characteristics, and methods of working with it. That's why below we will talk about the history of working with watercolor paint, the artists who contributed to its development, and its specific features.

Watercolor is a Latin word that means water-based paint, as well as "watercolor painting"²⁰⁴. Watercolor is widespread in ancient Egypt, Japan, China. Working with watercolors was developed in England two centuries ago. D. Cozens, Turner, D. Constable, R. Bonington, T. Artists such as Gjorten can be seen skillfully depicting the beautiful nature of England in their watercolor works.

In Central Asia, watercolor has long been used to beautifully decorate books. Among Central Asian artists, especially Kamoliddin Behzod gained great fame for his watercolor miniatures and illustrations for books.

At the end of the 19th century I. E. Repin, V. A. Serov, M. A. In the works of Russian artists such as Vrubel, watercolor showed its new qualities. And in Uzbekistan, the development of the art of watercolor painting by B. Hamdami, O'. Tansikboev, G. Shevyakov, especially Ch. It can be seen in Ahmarov's work.

The sophistication and refinement of the methods of working with watercolor paint led to the increase and diversity of its types. There are several types of watercolors available today, including hard, soft, and paste watercolors.

Watercolor brush is easy to apply, dissolves well in water. Aquaerl differs from other paints in that it lays on the surface of the paper in a thin layer, applies

²⁰³ Jabbarov B. G'. Basics of academic pencil drawing. Textbook. -T.: 2022. p. 7.

²⁰⁴ H. Egamov. Working with paints. - T.: 1981. p. 15.

evenly, smoothly, is placed and does not accumulate in one place in the form of a layer. If watercolor paint is not exposed to water for a long time, it will dry out too much and become difficult to use. That is why it is recommended to keep watercolor paint in a dark and cool place and protect it from sunlight. In addition, after using the "Leningrad" watercolor paint, which is considered the best quality, the surface of the colors in each tube should be lightly wiped with a clean brush and moistened.

A palette is used to mix paints. Not all paints have a palette. Therefore, students usually use white paper as a palette. However, it should not be forgotten that this has its own negative side. In the process of mixing paints on the surface of the paper, the paper freezes and becomes sticky, as a result, the glue contained in it mixes with the paint and negatively affects the quality of the watercolor. Therefore, it is recommended to use a palette quality from a regular window. Just don't forget to put white paper under the mirror. Otherwise, you may find that the color of something else under the mirror affects the appearance of the color you're mixing, resulting in a different shade than you intended.

Observing a certain order in placing colors on the palette helps the students to produce high-quality work, to move their eyes and hands freely, and to complete the work quickly.

It is recommended to put yellow, golden, red paints from warm colors on the palette first, and then green, blue, air color, purple colors. It is strictly forbidden to use overused, dirty brushes when mixing the colors on the palette. Therefore, it is necessary to wash the brush frequently in clean water. Otherwise, the remnants of the previously prepared color in the composition of the brush will be added to the color that we want to create later, creating a cold, dirty, dull look.

During any long-term practical training classes, the process of describing the performance can be divided into 4 stages. This includes the subject of working a still life image composed of two or more geometric objects on a neutral background.

Stage 1. First of all, the general structure of the installation, depending on the large size of the paper-weighted tablet, should be determined in an upright or lying position. Drawing begins with the correct placement of the general structure of the objects on the surface of the paper. It is also necessary to take into account that the insert does not remain large or small compared to the paper. Usually it is correct to place the insert on 4/3 of the paper. The external forms of the geometric bodies in the composition are carefully observed, the constructive structure of these forms is determined with the help of additional lines, and the purposes for which they are used in practice are analyzed. The ratio of height to width of each of the bodies is determined and their mutual ratio is also compared. General signs of bodies located on the outside - abris are found. When finding an outline, it is necessary to

pay special attention to the laws of linear perspective. Based on these, the objects in it are placed correctly relative to the paper and the plane of the object is found.

Object plane is the plane where the image of the object, module, image is located²⁰⁵. In this exercise, the plane on which the geometric objects are located is the product plane. It is necessary to correctly place objects in relation to the object plane. In most cases, students make a big mistake by finding the plane of the object only after they have first found the image of the objects. On the contrary, first of all, after finding the object plane, it is required to place objects on it.

One of the main tasks at this stage is to correctly find the light and shadows of these objects. Light, penumbra, true and falling shadows, reflections on objects are lightly defined with auxiliary lines. It should be emphasized here that it is not recommended to use too hard or too soft graphite pencils in drawing classes. Because hard pencils scratch the surface of the paper, spoil its quality, and are difficult to erase, while soft pencils fade during the erasing process. Therefore, it is recommended to use pencils of medium hardness and softness.

Stage 2. The main shape of all the objects in the composition and the mutual location and proportions of the small parts are re-examined and checked. At this stage, in connection with the transition to working with color, the excess, auxiliary lines created with the help of a graphite pencil in the first stage are erased. At this stage, the local colors of the objects in the set and the plane of the object, the fabric in the background are given in light colors. Since this task is grisaille work, it is done using different shades of black.

Grizaille - (French - "grizaille", "griz - gray") image created using gray, different shades of the same color²⁰⁶. Usually, painting in art schools begins with grayscale work. An image made using different shades of black is called grisaille. Brown, dark blue colors are also used in grisaille work.

Earlier watercolors contained white, but today's watercolors do not contain white. That is why the white color of the paper itself is used to reflect the lightest part of the composition. With this light, other light-shadow ratios are also found in the lightest shade compared to the darkest shade. When working with watercolor paint, the principle of transition from light to dark, from general to specific is slowly passed. In this, one of the main techniques of working in watercolors, which is intended for long-term work, is used.

Third stage. This stage is the stage of transition from the general to the private, to fragments. Each part of all objects in the composition is fully detailed based on the plane of the object, twists of fabrics, light and shadows, perspective laws. If the linear perspective is found in the first step, then the spatial perspective is also found. It should not be forgotten that spatiality is of great importance in all types of

²⁰⁵ Jabbarov B. G'. Basics of academic pencil drawing. Textbook. - T.: 2022. 14 - p.

²⁰⁶ Jabbarov B. G'. Basics of academic pencil drawing. Textbook. - T.: 2022. 14 - p.

painting. The brightest part of the objects in the image, penumbra, true and falling shadows are completely found. Reflections and materiality are also found, which are formed due to light returning from the plane of the object and falling from one object to another.

Step 4. This stage is the stage of generalization and rounding. It is required to achieve their integrity on the basis of correctly finding the character, specific shape and materiality of the objects in the composition. The objects in the composition must stand freely in the plane of the object, special attention is paid to the fact that the objects do not float in the air as if they are made of something lighter than paper or, on the contrary, as if they are made of a very heavy object, piercing the plane of the object and falling down. It is possible to independently analyze the mistakes and shortcomings made by the student by placing the image worked by the student side by side with the module and comparing them. The one who found the shortcomings should continue the work and eliminate them.

Conclusion

Along with the correct determination of color relationships during the process of painting, it should not be forgotten that we are working not only with simple color spots, but also on a specific form. The purpose of searching for color relationships is to find the nature and its dimensional form with the right color shades. If the color does not express the spatial location, materiality and exact shape of the object, it loses its meaning in the image. Light and dark, colored and colorless paint smears create materiality, color harmony and color only if they belong to a certain shape and object.

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